

doi 10.5281/zenodo.10991383

Vol. 07 Issue 03 March - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01284

***Aspergillus niger*, *Neurospora* sp. AND *Rhizopus* sp. AS AN ANTAGONISM FUNGI IN INHIBITING THE GROWTH OF *LASIODIPLODIA THEOBROMAE* (SRIKAYA FRUIT ROT PATHOGEN)**

By

I Made Sudarma* & Ni Nengah Darmiati*

*Lecturer in Agroecotechnology Study Program, Faculty of Agriculture, Udayana University, Jalan PB. Sudirman Denpasar

Corresponding author: madesudarma@unud.ac.id

Abstract

Srikaya fruit rot disease (*Annona squamosa* L.) is the main problem that affects the fruit when it is on the tree and after harvest. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out environmentally friendly alternative controls. Exophytic fungi such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizopus* sp. provided high inhibition against *Lasiodiplodia theobromae* (srikaya fruit rot pathogen) of $80.71 \pm 1.07\%$ and $82.92 \pm 0.50\%$, respectively. Meanwhile, the best endophytic fungus that is able to inhibit the growth of pathogens is *Neurospora* sp. and *Aspergillus* sp. with respective inhibition of $86.67 \pm 3.14\%$ and $88.35 \pm 0.46\%$ in vitro. In vivo test results showed that the fungi *A. niger* and *Aspergillus* sp. the best inhibition of each is 100%.

Keywords

***Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, exophytic and endophytic fungi, inhibited ability, in vitro and in vivo.**

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

INTRODUCTION

The srikaya plant (*Annona squamosa* L.) besides its edible fruit, is now widely used to prevent disease in the human body, such as the leaves can be used to treat as a vermicide, to treat tumors or cancer, insect bites, and other skin disease problems (1). Srikaya fruit extract can be used to inhibit the growth of several microbes such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Aspergillus niger*. The three extracts (acetone, ethanol, and aqueous) from srikaya show a positive effect on all of the above microorganisms (2).

Many diseases have been found to disturb sugar apple plants, these diseases include: *Pseudocercospora* fruit spot disease, *Diplodia* fruit rot, purple stripe (caused by *Phytophthora palmivora*), *Cylindrocladium colhounii* and *Cylindrocladium scoparium* fruit rot, and X disease (not yet identified) (3).

Lasiodiplodia theobromae is a fungus that has a fairly wide range of hosts and can cause diseases, such as mango fruit (4) and citrus stem rot (5). Pathogen that causes canker leaf blight and fruit rot in cocoa (6). As a cause of banana rot disease (7), as well as a cause of gummosis, branch death and mummification of citrus fruit (8).

Exophytic and endophytic microbes can now be used to control *L. theobromae*. *Bacillus velezensis* as endophytic bacteria is able to suppress the growth of *L. theobromae* on grapes (9). Endophytic fungi are wide spread and reside within plant cells for at least part of their lives without causing any symptoms of infection. Different host plants may have different levels of fungal endophytes and community composition. However, the association of fungal endophytes with host plants and their hostile behavior remains unknown (10). According to Maubasher *et al.* (2022) (11) stated that endophytic fungi are 1). Microfungi that live in host plant tissues intercellularly and/or intracellularly without clear pathological symptoms. 2). In order to maintain a stable symbiosis, endophytes secrete chemicals to help plants adapt to harsh environments. 3). As a treasure trove of bioactive metabolites, endophytic fungi are a sustainable source of various natural products namely: quinones, saponins, alkaloids, steroids, phenolic acids, terpenoids and tannins that exhibit antimicrobial and anti cancer properties.

Phylloplane fungi are mycotic fungi that grow on plant surfaces (12). There are groups of phylloplane fungi: resident (staying still) and casual (accidental). Residents can reproduce on healthy leaf surfaces without affecting the host while casuals land on leaf surfaces but cannot grow (13).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Place and time of research

The research was carried out in two places: 1) looking for diseased and healthy plant specimens from cocoa plants planted in the Jimbaran Hill area. 2) Plant Disease Laboratory and Agricultural Biotechnology Laboratory. The research was carried out from April to August 2022.

Identification of Endophytic and Exophytic Fungi

The stored endophytic and exophytic fungi were then grown in Petri dishes containing PDA and repeated 5 times. Cultures were incubated in the dark at room temperature ($\pm 27^{\circ}\text{C}$). Isolates were identified macroscopically after 3 days to determine the color of the colony and growth rate, and identified microscopically to determine the septa on the hyphae, the shape of the spores/condia and sporangioophores. Identification of fungi using reference books (14, 15, 16, 17).

Test of the Inhibited Ability of Endophytic and Exophytic Fungi Against Pathogens

The endophytic and exophytic fungi found were each tested for their inhibitory power against the growth of pathogenic fungi using the dual culture technique (in one Petri dish each pathogenic fungus was grown flanked by two endophytic fungi). The resistance can be calculated as follows (18, 19): Inhibited ability (%) = $A-B/A \times 100\%$. Where: A = diameter of *L. theobromae* colonies in single culture (mm), and B = diameter of *L. theobromae* colonies in dual culture (mm).

Prevalence of Endophytic and Exophytic Fungi

Determining the prevalence of endophytic and exophytic fungi is based on the frequency of endophytic and exophytic fungal isolates found (leaves, stems, flowers and fruit) per Petri dish, divided by all isolates found times 100%. The prevalence of isolates will determine the dominance of endophytic fungi in healthy sugar apple plant parts.

In Vivo Antagonist Test

The in vivo antagonistic test for endophytic and exophytic fungi was found by pricking fresh fruit with a spelden needle 20 times, then smearing it with antagonistic fungal spores (spores from one Petri dish in 250 ml of sterile distilled water), then dipping them in the fungalspore suspension. Endophytic and exophytic fungi found include:

K-P = Control without pathogen

A = control (without being treated with antagonist) B = antagonist treatment 1 (spore suspension 5×10^7) C = antagonist treatment 2 (spore suspension 5×10^7) D = antagonist treatment 3 (spore suspension 5×10^7) E = antagonist treatment 4 (spore suspension 5×10^7) F = antagonist treatment 5 (spore suspension 5×10^7) K+P = control with pathogen

All treatments were repeated 5 times. The experiment was designed with a randomized block design (RBD), and after analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out, it was continued with the least significant difference test (LSD) at the 5% level. The attack parameters are measured using the formulation: how many punctures are attacked by the fungus divided by all punctures (20 x) times 100%.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Exophytic and Endophytic Fungi

Exophytic and endophytic fungi originating from fruit, leaves and twigs were isolated using 1 g of material. The types of fungi found were *Aspergillus* sp., *Aspergillus niger*, *Neurospora* sp., *Fusarium* sp., *Rhizopus* sp., *Penicillium* sp., and *Mycelia sterilia* (Table 1)

Table 1. Types of exophytic and endophytic fungi originating from fruit, leaves and twigs

No.	Exophytic fungi	Number of isolate	Endophytic fungi	Number of isolate
	Fruit		Fruit	
1	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	3 (20%)*	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	6 (40%)
2	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	9 (60%)	<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	3 (20%)
3	<i>Miselia sterilia</i>	3 (20%)	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	3 (20%)
4			<i>Miselia sterilia</i>	3 (20%)

Total	15		15
Leaf		Leaf	
1 <i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	6 (40%)	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	9 (60%)
2 <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	6 (40%)	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	3 (20%)
3 <i>Neurospora</i> sp.	3 (40%)	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	3 (20%)
Total	15		15
Twig		Twig	
1 <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	3 (20%)	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	6 (40%)
2 <i>Fusarium</i> sp.	3 (20%)	<i>Miselia sterilia</i>	9 (60%)
3 <i>Rhizopus</i> sp	9 (60%)		
Total	15		15

* Prevalence of fungi found during the study

The fungi that dominate (highest prevalence) exophyte types are *A. niger* and *Rhizopus* sp. with 9 isolates (60%), while the dominant fungal endophyte was *Fusarium* sp. and *Miselia sterilia* with 9 isolates (60%). The diversity of endophytic fungi in the phylloplane is on the surface of plant parts, and endophytes are in the inner tissues. Endophytes are known to be microbes that live in plants that are neutral or beneficial to the host plant. Specifically bacteria or fungi, and there may be 3 types: 1) other host pathogens that are not pathogenic in their endophytic relationships, 2) non-pathogenic microbes, and 3) pathogens that are not pathogenic but are still able to colonize through selection methods or genetic change (20). Plant endophytic fungi are important and useful as sources of natural bioactive compounds with potential applications in agriculture, medicine and the food industry. Many useful bioactive compounds with antimicrobial, insecticidal, cytotoxic and anti-cancer properties have been successfully investigated from endophytic fungi. Over long periods of coevolution, friendly relationships have been established between each endophyte and its host.

Aspergillus is a phylloplane fungus found on healthy leaves of Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. (Moench) (21)]. The phyllosphere refers to the plant's entire aerial habitat, while the phylloplane describes the entire surface of the leaf. The phylloplane provides a home for a diversified microbial community and is thus a ecosystems are important both ecologically and economically. For many years, phylloplane inhabitants have been studied as bioprotectors and growth enhancers of host plants. Plant and phylloplane-microbe interactions result in increased fitness and productivity of agricultural plants (22). Study of phylloplane microflora in various plants Research has been carried out, it was found that many fungi *A. flavus*, *A. niger* and *Trichoderma* sp. Their abundance contributed 6.97% and 3.84% respectively (23). There are three types of fungi that inhabit the phylloplane of safflower (sunflower) plants. including *A. niger*, *Penicillium* sp. and *T. viride* (24).

Inhibited Ability of Exophytic and Endophytic Fungi

The inhibited ability of exophytic fungi against pathogens (*L. theobromae*) ranged from $60.32 \pm 1.50\%$ to $82.92 \pm 0.50\%$ (highest by the fungus *Rhizopus* sp.). Meanwhile, the inhibitory power of endophytic fungi ranged from $68.20 \pm 1.49\%$ to $88.35 \pm 0.46\%$ (the highest was *Aspergillus* sp.) (Table 2). All exophytic and endophytic fungi show inhibition of pathogens through competition for space and nutrients. It is proven that antagonistic fungi always grow faster and fill the petri dish until the pathogen cannot get food and then dies.

The endophytic fungus that dominates in suppressing pineapple fruit rot caused by *Neoscytalidium dimidiatum* (Penz.) Crous & Slippers, is the fungus *Rhizopus* sp., and the highest inhibitory power is achieved by *Neurospora* sp., *Rizopus* sp. and *A. flavus* (25). Next, the ability to

produce phytase and amylase enzymes by *A. niger*, *R. oryzae* and *N. sitophila* was tested using sterilized tofu dregs. Phytase and amylase enzymes are enzymes that are widely used in the food, feed and health industry sectors (26).

The *in vivo* inhibition test showed that all treatments were significantly different from the control plus pathogen. The highest inhibitory power was achieved by treating *Aspergillus* sp. and *A. niger* each reached $100 \pm 0\%$, and the lowest was achieved by *Rhizopus* sp. amounted to $70 \pm 1.5\%$, and was significantly different from controls without pathogens and controls with pathogens (Table 3).

Table 2. Test the inhibited ability of exophytic and endophytic fungi

Fungi origin	Name of fungi	Inhibited ability (%)
1. Eksofit daun 1	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	60,32±1,50
2. Eksofit daun 2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	65,21±2,50
3. Eksofit daun 3	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	68,64±1,59
4. Eksofit daun 4	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	75,15±2,24
5. Eksofit daun 5	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	74,69±0,72
6. Eksofit buah 1	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	65,68±0,82
7. Eksofit buah 2	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	65,21±1,50
8. Eksofit buah 3	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,32±2,30
9. Eksofit buah 4	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	72,00±0,31
10. Eksofit buah 5	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	80,71±1,07*
11. Eksofit ranting 1	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	75, 14±1,50
12. Eksofit ranting 2	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	71,31±0,68
13. Eksofit ranting 3	<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	82,92±0,50*
14. Eksofit ranting 4	<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	76,67±3,27
15. Eksofit ranting 5	<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	82,22±3,27*
16. Endofit daun 1	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	81,85±0,52*
17. Endofit daun 2	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	86,67±3,14*
18. Endofit daun 3	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	78,15±4,19
19. Endofit daun 4	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	88,35±0,46*
20. Endofit daun 5	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	78,26±1,22
21. Endofit ranting 1	Miselia sterilia	68,20±1,49
22. Endofit ranting 2	Miselia sterilia	75,92±2,62
23. Endofit ranting 3	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,23±2,10
24. Endofit ranting 4	Miselia sterilia	71,85±0,52
25. Endofit ranting 5	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	75,25±1,20
26. Endofit buah 1	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,05±2,20
27. Endofit buah 2	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,55±1,30
28. Endofit buah 3	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,32±2,10
29. Endofit buah 4	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,23±1,30
30. Endofit buah 5	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	70,15±0,80

* Continue to determine the inhibited ability *in vivo*

Table 3. The of the inhibited ability exophytic and endophytic fungi *in vivo*

Treatment.	Fungi origin	Name of fungi	Disease incidence (%)		Inhibited ability (%)	
K-P	Control without pathogen		0±0.0	a*	100±0.0	a*
A	Leaf endophytic 4	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	0±0.0	a	100±0.0	a
B	Leaf exophytic 5	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	0±0.0	a	100±0.0	a
C	Leaf endophytic 1	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	3±0.8	ab	97±0.8	ab
D	Leaf endophytic 2	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	7±1.2	ab	93±1.2	ab
E	Twig exophytic 5	<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	15±1.6	ab	85±1.6	ab
F	Twig exophytic 3	<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	30±0.9	b	70±0.9	b
K+P	Control with pathogen	<i>Lasioidiplodia theobromae</i>	70±2.0	c	30±2.0	c

* Least significant difference test (LSD) at the 5% level.

Endophytic fungi in particular are asexual, for example systemic endophytes in grasses, are generally seen as mutually beneficial to plants primarily through the action of mycotoxins, such as grass-infecting alkaloids, which protect the plant host from herbivores. Much of the evidence for the concept of mutual defence comes from agronomic studies of grass cultivars, especially some endophyte-host interactions (27).

Aspergillus flavus suppressed the maximum growth of *Alternaria brassicae*, the influence of volatile and non-volatile metabolite compounds released by phylloplane fungi was also observed (28). According to Thakur and Harsh (2016) (29) stated that the phylloplane fungus *A. niger* can suppress *Alternaria alternata* on Sarpagandha (*Rauwolfia serpentina*) plants by 50%. Borgohain and Chutia (2014) (30) stated that *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Fusarium* sp. is a phylloplane fungus found on castor plants (*Ricinus communis* L.). Meanwhile, *A. fumiguloris*, *Aspergillus* sp. and *F. moniliforme* has been isolated from the phylloplane of the medicinal plant (*Azadirachta indica*). These medicinal plants release phytochemical compounds in the form of flavonoids, cardiac glycosides and terpenoids (31). *Rhizopus* sp. is a phylloplane fungus that dominates mature leaves on Muga host plants (32).

CONCLUSION

Srikaya fruit rot disease (*Annona squamosa* L.) is the main problem that affects the fruit when it is on the tree and after harvest. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out environmentally friendly alternative controls. Exophytic fungi such as *A. niger* and *Rhizopus* sp. provided high inhibition against *L. theobromae* (srikaya fruit rot pathogen) of $80.71 \pm 1.07\%$ and $82.92 \pm 0.50\%$, respectively. Meanwhile, the best endophytic fungus that is able to inhibit the growth of pathogens is *Neurospora* sp. and *Aspergillus* sp. with respective inhibition of $86.67 \pm 3.14\%$ and $88.35 \pm 0.46\%$ *in vitro*. *In vivo* test results showed that the fungi *A. niger* and *Aspergillus* sp. the best inhibition of each is 100%.

Acknowledgements

Authors wish to thank to the Rector of Udayana University for their assistance and the opportunity given so that research can be resolved, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, Udayana University, and Chairman of the Institute for Research and Community Service Udayana University, for their help and cooperation so that research can be funded to completion.

REFERENCES

- (1) Saha, R. 2011. Pharmacognosy and pharmacology of *Annona squamosa* L.: A review. Int. J. of Phar, & Life Sci. (IJPLS) 2(10): 1183-1189.
- (2) Vijayalakshmi, R. and T. Nithiya. 2015. Antimicrobial activity of fruit extract of *Annona squamosa* L.). World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 4(5):1257-1267.
- (3) Agrilink. 1998. Custard apple information kit. Queensland Government. Reprint-Information Current in 1998. 1-26 h.
- (4) Kamil F.H., E.E. Saeed, K.A. El-Tarabily. 2018. Biological Control of Mango Dieback Disease Caused by *Lasiodyplodia theobromae* Using Streptomycete and Non-streptomycete Actinobacteria in the United Arab Emirates. Front. Microbiol. 9:829.
- (5) Dwiastuti M.E. and T.G. Aji. 2021. Citrus stem rot disease (*Lasiodyplodia theobromae*(Pat.) Griff. & Maubl) problem and their control strategy in Indonesia. IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science 752 (2021) 012030.
- (6) Huda-Shakirah, A.R., N.M.I.M. Nor, L. Zakaria, Y.H. Leong and Masratul. 2022. *Lasiodyplodia theobromae* as a causal pathogen of leaf blight, stem canker, and pod rot of *Theobromae cacao* in Malaysia. Scientific Report 12: 8966.
- (7) Sangeetha, G., A. Anandan and S. Usha Rani. 2011. Morphological and molecular characterisation of *Lasiodyplodia theobromae* from various banana cultivars causing crown rot disease in fruits, Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection, DOI:10.1080/03235408.2011.587986.
- (8) Hernández, H.F., J. F. Gracia, S. E.V. Fuentes, A.P. Rodríguez, A. A. Domínguez, A. Monteon-Ojeda. 2021. Report of *Lasiodyplodia theobromae* (Pat.) Griffon and Maubl. in citrus trees in Tamaulipas. Revista Mexicana Ciencias Agrícolas 12(3): 499- 511.
- (9) Saucedo-Bazalar M., P. Masias, E. Nouchi-Moromizato, C. Santos, E. Mialhe, V. Cedeño. 2023. MALDI mass spectrometry-based identification of antifungal molecules from endophytic *Bacillus* strains with biocontrol potential of *Lasiodyplodia theobromae*, a grapevine trunk pathogen in Peru. Elsevier B.V. Curr Res Microb Sci. doi: 10.1016/j.crmicr.2023.100201.
- (10) Segaran, G. and M. Sathivelu. 2023. Fungicidal and plant growth-promoting traits of *Lasiodyplodia pseudotheobromae*, an endophyte from *Andrographis paniculata*. Front.Plant Sci., 14.
- (11) Moubasher, H.A., B. A. Balbool, Y. A. Helmy, A. M. Alsuhaibani, A.A. Atta, D. H. Sheir, and A.M. Abdel-Azeem. 2022. Insights into Asparaginase from Endophytic Fungus *Lasiodyplodia theobromae*: Purification, Characterization and Antileukemic Activity. International Journal Environmental Research and Public Health 19(2): 680.
- (12) Langvad, F. 1980. A simple and rapid method for qualitative and quantitative study of the fungal flora of leave. *Canadian Journal of Botany* 26: 666-670.
- (13) Leben, C. 1965. Epiphytic micro-organisms in relation to plant diseases. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 2: 209-230.
- (14) Samson, R.A., E.S. Hoekstra, and C. A.N. Van Oorschot. 1981. Introduction to Food-Borne Fungi. Centraalbureau Voor-Schimmelcultures. Institute of The Royal Netherlands. Academic of Arts and Sciences.
- (15) Pitt, J.I. and A.D. Hocking. 1997. Fungi and Food Spoilage. Blackie Academic and Professional. Second Edition. London-Weinhein-New York-Tokyo-Melbourne-Madras.
- (16) Barnett, H.L. and B.B. Hunter. 1998. Illustrated Genera of Imperfect Fungi. APS Press. The American Phytopathological Society. St Paul, Minnesota.

- (17) Indrawati. G., R.A. Samson, K. Van den Tweel-Vermeulen, A. Oetari dan I. Santoso. 1999. Pengenalan Kapang Tropik Umum. Yayasan Obor Indonesia. Universitas Indonesia (University of Indonesia Culture Collection) Depok, Indonesia dan Centraalbureau voor Schimmelfcultures, Baarn, The Netherlands.
- (18) Dolar, F.S. 2001. Antagonistic effect of *Aspergillus melleus* Yukawa on soilborne pathogens of Chickpea. *Tarim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 8(2): 167-170.
- (19) Mojica-Marin, V., H. A. Luna-Olvera, C. Fco, Sandoval-Coronado, B. Pereyra- Alférez, H. Lilia, Morales-Ramos, E. Carlos, Hernández-Luna and G. O. Alvarado- Gomez. 2008. Antagonistic activity of selected strains of *Bacillus thuringiensis* against *Rhizoctonia solani* of chili pepper. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 7 (9): 1271-1276.
- (20) Backman, P.A., and R.A. Sikora. 2008. Endophytic: an emerging tool for biological control. *Biological Control*. doi: 10.1016/j.biocontrol.2008.03.009.
- (21) Ogwu, M.C. and M.E. Osawaru. 2014. Comparative Study of Microflora Population on the Phylloplane of Common Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. (Moench.)]. *Ig. J. Biotech.* 28: 17-25.
- (22) Goswami, S., N. Goel and R.S. Majumdar. 2021. Phylloplane microbes impact host physiology: a review. *Journal of Plant Protection Research* 61(3):213-221.
- (23) Chauhan D., Sanjay and Navneet. 2010. Studies on phylloplane microflora of different tree species. *Proc.Nat.Acad.Sci. India* 80 (3): 254-258.
- (24) Mandhare V.K. and A.V. Suryawanshi. 2009. Phylloplane Microflora of Safflower. *Agric. Sci. Digest.* 29(2): 1-2.
- (25) Sudarma I M., N.W. Suniti and N.N. Darmiati. 2022. The Role of Exophytic and Endophytic Microbes in Controlling Fruit Rot Disease on Pineapple (*Ananas comosus*(L.) Merr. *GPH – Journal of Agriculture and Research* 5(7): 7-18.
- (26) Kanti A. 2017. The Potential of *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Neurospora sitophila* to Produce Phytase and Amylase Enzyme on Soybean Curd Residue. *Buletin Peternakan* Vol. 41 (1): 26-36.
- (27) Faeth, S. H. 2002. Are endophytic fungi defensive plant mutualists? – *Oikos* 98: 25–36.
- (28) Yadav, S.L., A.K. Mishra, P.N. Dongre and Rashmin Singh. 2011. Assessment of fungitoxicity of phylloplane fungi against *Alternaria brassicae* causing leaf spot of mustard. *Journal of Agricultural Technology* 7(6): 1823-1831.
- (30) Borgohain, A., R. Das and M. Chutia. 2014. Fungal diversity in phylloplane of castorplant (*Ricinus communis* L.): the primary food plant of Eri Silkworm. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science* 4(2): 82-86.
- (31) Prabakaran, M., S. Merinal, and A. Panneerelvan. 2011. Investigation of phylloplane mycoflora from some medicinal plants. *European Journal of Experimental Biology* 1(2): 219-225.
- Ray, M.K., P.K. Mishra, P.K. Baruah, and D. Choudhry. 2014. Isolation and a comparative study of phylloplane mycoflora of Muga host plants Som dan Sulau from Goalpara district of Assam. *International Journal and Applied Bioscience* 1(6): 78-83.